

1 **Laboratory Investigation of Grouted Coupler Connection Details for Accelerated Bridge**
2 **Construction**

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1 **ABSTRACT**

2 This paper presents a laboratory investigation on the performance of grouted reinforcing bar couplers with
3 the connection details similar to those utilized on the precast concrete elements of the Keg Creek Bridge
4 on US 6 in Iowa. The testing program consisted of a series of static load tests, a fatigue test and
5 evaluation of the chloride penetration resistance of laboratory specimens. The goal of this testing was to
6 evaluate the ability of the grouted reinforcing bar couplers to develop flexural capacity at the joint
7 between the precast elements as well as the durability of the connection. For structural load testing, seven
8 full-scale specimens, each with #14 epoxy-coated reinforcing bars spliced by epoxy-coated grouted
9 couplers, were fabricated and tested in three different loading cases: four-point bending, axial-tension
10 plus bending and a cyclic test of the system in bending. The static load testing demonstrated that the
11 applied axial load had a minimal effect on the formation of cracks and overall performance of the
12 connection. When ultra-high performance concrete was used as a bedding grout, the initiation of crack
13 was slightly delayed but no considerable improvement was observed in terms of the magnitude of the
14 crack width during loading or the crack closure upon unloading. The results of the seventh specimen,
15 tested in fatigue to 1 million cycles, showed little global displacement and crack width throughout the
16 test, neither of which expanded measurably. No evidence of moisture or chloride penetration was detected
17 at the grouted joint during the six-month monitoring.

18 **Keywords:** Grouted Coupler, Accelerated Bridge Construction, Load Testing, Chloride Penetration.

1 INTRODUCTION

2 With the increase in demand for precast structural elements, the use of accelerated bridge
3 construction (ABC) technologies has become an integral part in bridge construction as it offers many
4 benefits such as reducing construction duration, improving work zone safety, minimizing temporary
5 roadway construction, and reducing user costs and other related impacts on traffic (1). In recent decades,
6 numerous studies have been conducted to evaluate the means to connect precast elements. NCHRP
7 Report 698 (2) summarized results of a series of literature study and survey on ABC connections that
8 have been utilized or being researched. The report analyzed and categorized various types of connections
9 in terms of the force transfer mechanism: such as bar couplers, grouted ducts, pocket connections, socket
10 connections, hybrid connections, integral connections, and emerging connection technologies. Although
11 some studies (3 – 6) have shown that mechanically spliced connections could provide emulative behavior
12 without deviating substantially from conventional design procedures and details, these studies do not
13 provide information as to how the mechanical splices can be used in the design and construction of the
14 precast bridge columns that conform to US standards.

15 Among the various types of connection methodologies, grouted rebar couplers have recently
16 received considerable attention as they are known to allow for a quick and relatively easy means to
17 connect precast concrete elements. A grouted rebar coupler is a proprietary mechanical device that is
18 filled with cementitious grout as bonding material, and can be used to splice reinforcing steel within
19 precast elements and provide a continuity to the connection during a load transfer. In a typical application,
20 reinforcing bars are inserted into the ends of a coupler and meet at mid-length as the grout is injected into
21 the coupler. Bridge engineers and contractors now recognize the benefits of using grouted rebar couplers
22 in that it would accelerate the speed of construction, increase productivity and simplify design details.
23 The University of Nevada at Reno investigated bridge column-footing components that were connected
24 by means of grouted splice sleeves (GSS) (7). In this study, GSS was utilized in two specimens and the
25 third one was cast monolithically as a benchmark specimen. Test results indicated that plastic
26 deformation did not occur in the plastic hinge region due to the relatively high rigidity of the column
27 section over the splice sleeve region (i.e., spliced rebar failed in the footing near the column-footing
28 interface). The study pointed out that there was a similar performance in all specimens in terms of
29 ultimate load capacity, energy dissipation and pushover response, but not ductility capacity. The
30 Michigan department of transportation (DOT) investigated two proprietary grout-filled mechanical
31 reinforcement splices for suitability in connecting precast concrete structural elements (8). The
32 experimental program was composed of slip, fatigue, ultimate load, and creep testing. The test results
33 indicated that both splices met the AASHTO LRFD (9) provisions for slip and fatigue, and there were no
34 significant creep displacements under sustained loading. The ultimate load capacity exceeded 125
35 percent of the yield strength of reinforcing steel. The study indicated that the ultimate load capacity
36 might be lowered when epoxy coated rebar was used.

37 While the ABC is gaining popularity and more frequently adapted by bridge engineering
38 communities, it often results in the use of newly developed or modified connection details that are
39 sometimes untested, under-evaluated and/or unfamiliar to bridge engineers and contractors (10). The
40 majority of the published research and testing on this type of connections has focused mainly on a direct
41 tension test that may not represent the condition of a realistic application. One example is the Keg Creek
42 Bridge that utilized the grouted couplers in the region where the primary loading was axial compression
43 from gravity loads and bending due to thermal and live loads (10). Moreover, previous studies have
44 shown that not all connection details function in the ABC bridge application as they are often times
45 prompted by their developers. Therefore, it is important that the connection details be evaluated in the
46 form which they are or will be utilized in a specific ABC process such that their integrity and
47 performance in both short- and long-term can be properly assessed.

48 Sponsored by the Iowa DOT, the Bridge Engineering Center at Iowa State University conducted a
49 series of laboratory testing of an ABC connection detail utilizing sleeve-lock grouted rebar couplers. The
50 primary objective of this study was to evaluate the performance and durability of grouted reinforcing bar
51 couplers with the connection details similar to those utilized on the precast concrete elements of the Keg

1 Creek Bridge on US 6 in Pottawattamie County, Iowa – a 210 ft-long and 47 ft-wide steel/precast bridge
2 that was completely replaced with only two weeks of traffic-closure. In addition to the speedy
3 construction schedule, this study also sought to demonstrate the possibility and viability of this type of
4 connection methods to be duplicated with other similar bridge replacement/construction projects
5 throughout the US. The grouted joints between the pier column and the pier cap and between the drilled
6 shaft and the pier column were the main focus of this investigation.

8 EXPERIMENTAL PROGRAM

9 In the design of the laboratory experiment, considerations were given to address some of the key
10 factors so that the test results would represent the performance of the coupled connections on the Keg
11 Creek Bridge. Such considerations included the use of the same size and brand of the couplers used on the
12 Keg Creek Bridge (#14 epoxy-coated grouted steel couplers from Dayton Superior), and testing the
13 couplers subjected to both pure-axial tension and bending. To this end, it was decided to make a specimen
14 in a rectangular cross-section with two #14 epoxy-coated reinforcing bars that were spliced by epoxy-
15 coated grouted reinforcing bar couplers placed closed to the extreme tension face as shown in **Figure 1**
16 (10).

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20 **Figure 1 Reinforcement layout of a testing specimen**

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22 A precast element system was constructed for testing in the laboratory to investigate the couplers
23 in a realistic application. During the fabrication, the frames of the two sections were laid side to side with
24 concrete cast horizontally for ease of construction and adequate consolidation of the concrete around the
25 reinforcing bars and couplers. Once cured, the specimen was then reoriented vertically to simulate the
26 condition of the Keg Creek Bridge. Prior to the application of the grouts to the joint, the interface was
27 treated with either a sandblasting or a foam retarder; a dam was installed around the top surface of the
28 bottom specimen to contain the grout for the grout bed; and shims were placed to prevent the grouts from
29 being pressed out of the joint so that a specific grout bed depth could be obtained (**Figure 2**). In addition,
30 sleeve-lock seal plugs were utilized on the protruding reinforcing bars to keep the bedding grout from
31 penetrating into the couplers. Following the application of the bedding grout at the joint, the two sections
32 were assembled vertically by lowering the top section onto the bottom section, inserting the exposed
33 reinforcement projecting from the end of the member being connected into the open ends of the adjoining
34 unit. Then, the couplers were grouted with Dayton Superior Sleeve-Lock Grout using a grout pump.

35 A total of seven full-scale specimens were constructed and tested in a four-point bending
36 configuration. Six specimens were statically tested and the seventh specimen was tested in fatigue. The

1 precast joint of the Specimens 1 through 5 utilized W. R. Meadows 588-10k grout for the bedding
 2 material, the same materials used on the Keg Creek Bridge, while ultra-high performance concrete
 3 (UHPC) bedding grouts were used on the other two specimens. **Table 1** presents the specifics of each of
 4 the seven specimens. The 28-day compressive strengths of all bedding and coupler grouts obtained from a
 5 series of compression testing were 8,960 psi for the W.R. Meadows bedding grouts, 10,700 psi for the
 6 Dayton sleeve-lock grouts, and 17,490 psi for the UHPC mix.
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10 **Figure 2 Dam and shims placed at the interface to contain the bedding grout**

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TABLE 1 Measurement Conversion

Specimen ID	Loading	Joint Prep	Joint Grout	Axial Load
Specimen 1	Static; L/2	Sand Blast	W. R. Meadows 588-10k	NA
Specimen 2	Static; L/3	Sand Blast	W. R. Meadows 588-10k	NA
Specimen 3	Static; L/3	Sand Blast	W. R. Meadows 588-10k	NA
Specimen 4	Static; L/3	Sand Blast	W. R. Meadows 588-10k	54k
Specimen 5	Static; L/3	Sand Blast	W. R. Meadows 588-10k	115k
Specimen 6	Static; L/3	Form Retarder	UHPC	54k
Specimen 7	Fatigue; L/3	Form Retarder	UHPC	NA

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For the laboratory testing, it was important to simulate the loading mechanism in the connection details of the Keg Creek Bridge, i.e., axial compression mainly due to gravity loads, and bending due to both thermal effects and live loads from the superstructure. After considering different options, a decision was made to test each specimen in a horizontal position such that the grouted couplers placed in the tension region of the specimen. The reason for the horizontal orientation was because (i) one could avoid the complicated fixed connection detail that would have been required if tested vertically; and (ii) it allowed for the elimination of shear effects and application of greater loads. The three loading cases utilized were bending, axial load plus bending, and a cyclic test of the system in bending. The main goal of the structural load testing was to evaluate the ability of the grouted reinforcing bar couplers to develop flexural capacity between the precast elements, a simulated pier column connection to a drilled shaft or

1 pier foundation of the Keg Creek Bridge. Prior to the load testing, each specimen was inspected for any
2 signs of cracking at the grouted joint and no cracks were observed.

3 Each specimen was instrumented with a global deflection transducer, crack-meters and strain
4 gauges. The deflection transducer was installed at midspan of each specimen to collect applied load
5 versus deflection data. Two crack meters were mounted on the bottom surface of the specimen across the
6 grouted joint in line with each of the grouted couplers. A total of eight strain gauges were installed, four
7 on the bottom of the specimen in line with the grouted couplers and four on the side of the specimen
8 directly below the load points near the top and bottom edges.

9 For initial static load testing, Specimens 1 through 3 were loaded in four-point bending to
10 approximately 360 kips using a 400k hydraulic actuator and a hand pump with no axial load applied.
11 Since the static load testing was intended to assess the performance and durability of the grouted joint
12 under loading (i.e., cracking of the joint), the specimen was not loaded to ultimate load/failure. The first
13 specimen (Specimen 1) was loaded with a load configuration of the span length (L) divided by 2 (L/2) for
14 the four-point bending setup. Subsequent to the testing of the first specimen, the research team decided to
15 change the load configuration of the remaining specimens from L/2 to L/3 as shown in **Figure 3** to
16 increase the bending moment, widen the crack at the joint and observe if the crack would close after the
17 removal of the load. In addition, an axial load (54 kips or 115 kips) was included along with the four-
18 point bending in the testing of Specimens 4 through 6 to simulate the in-service connection condition of
19 the precast elements of the Keg Creek Bridge. For fatigue testing, Specimen 7 was loaded at a point load
20 of 106 kips utilizing a 225k actuator and a computer-controlled hydraulic pump in a four-point bending
21 setup at approximately 1 Hz for 1 million cycles such that the two coupled #14 reinforcing bars were
22 stressed to 18 ksi in accordance with the AASHTO LRFD Design Specifications (9).

23 In addition to the structural load testing, three additional, small-scale specimens were cast to
24 investigate the susceptibility of the coupled connections to chloride penetration, which is of concern to
25 bridges exposed to de-icing agents. Each of these specimens was 8 in. in diameter and consisted of #14
26 epoxy-coated steel bars spliced with a grouted coupler placed in the center of the specimen (**Figure 4**).
27 The same bedding and coupler grouts that were used on the Keg Creek Bridge were used in these
28 specimens. Once grouted and fully assembled, each of the three specimens was instrumented with a
29 corrosion wire, placed in a 3% chloride solution bath, and monitored for six months with readings taken
30 periodically.

31 32 **TEST RESULTS**

33 Presented in **Figures 5 through 10** are the moment versus crack width plots from the static load
34 testing with the moment being the calculated moment at the joint and the crack width collected from the
35 two crack meters, labeled Crack 1 and Crack 2. Before the testing was carried out, it was expected that the
36 joint crack would close up with the removal of loading. This can be observed on Specimens 1 and 3
37 (**Figures 5 and 7**). The result of the Specimen 2, however, show that a good closure of crack was not
38 obtained, which is believed to be due to the peak load that was sustained for a longer period of time
39 during the testing of Specimen 2 for documentation and observation of the crack. The crack widths of
40 Specimens 4 and 5 that were loaded in four-point bending with an axial load of 54 kips and 115 kips,
41 respectively, were slightly lower at the peak load than those of Specimen 1 and 3, and the residual crack
42 widths were approximately 50% of Specimens 1 and 3 upon the removal of the applied load.

43 For Specimens 1 through 5, the crack seemed to form at one of the concrete-to-grout interfaces
44 almost immediately after they were loaded. It was speculated that it was the result of debonding of the
45 grout upon loading. Based on this observation, Specimen 6 was fabricated using UHPC as a bedding
46 grout and tested in four-point bending with an axial load of 54 kips. While the crack closure and width
47 showed similar results, one noticeable difference of Specimen 6 from the previous five specimens was
48 that the crack did not start to form until 13 ft-k indicating that the initiation of crack upon loading was
49 slightly delayed by utilizing the UHPC bedding grout.

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3 (a) Typical four-point bending test setup

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6 (b) L/2 setup

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9 (c) L/3 setup

10 **Figure 3 Illustration of test specimen and four-point bending test setup**

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2 **Figure 4 Cross-section view of specimens for chloride penetration test**
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5 **Figure 5 Moment versus crack width for Specimen 1**

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2 **Figure 6 Moment versus crack width for Specimen 2**

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5 **Figure 7 Moment versus crack width for Specimen 3**

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8 **Figure 8 Moment versus crack width for Specimen 4**

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3 **Figure 9 Moment versus crack width for Specimen 5**

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6 **Figure 10 Moment versus crack width for Specimen 6**

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8 **Figures 11 and 12** present the global deflection and the crack width during the fatigue testing
9 conducted on Specimen 7. The test result shows that the maximum global deflection was about 0.18 in.,
10 and that the maximum crack width throughout the duration of the 1-million plus cycles was
11 approximately 0.02 in, which is less than half of what was observed during the static load testing. This
12 was expected given the reduced loading in the fatigue testing. Overall, the fatigue test results revealed that
13 there were little to no creep in global deflection or crack growth at the interface. Upon the completion of
14 the testing, the reading on the crack meter returned to almost zero indicating that the crack at the joint
15 closed up well with the removal of the applied load.

16 Readings taken during the chloride penetration test of the three small specimens showed no
17 indication that the reinforcing steel was corroding. This can be attributed to the fact that the joints were
18 kept uncracked when submerged in the chloride bath and, thereby, not allowing the chloride to penetrate
19 into the specimens and their grout beds. While the reinforcing steel embedded in the specimens were
20 epoxy coated, the inside of the coupler was not. Because of this concern, each specimen was broken apart
21 at the grout bed at the conclusion of the six-month monitoring and visually inspected. No evidence of
22 moisture or chloride penetration was detected.

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3 **Figure 11 Global displacement for Specimen 7 – fatigue test**

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6 **Figure 12 Crack width for Specimen 7 – fatigue test.**

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8 **SUMMARY AND CONCLUDING REMARKS**

9 While the ABC is gaining the popularity and frequently adapted in bridge construction, it often
10 results in the use of newly developed or modified technologies that are sometimes untested or under

1 evaluated, especially when used in a new application. An example of such technology is the grouted
2 reinforcing bar coupler that is often used to connect precast bridge elements. The majority of the
3 published research and testing on this type of connection has focused mainly on a direct tension test that
4 may not represent the condition of a realistic application, particularly the Keg Creek Bridge on US 6 in
5 Iowa that utilized the grouted couplers in the region where the primary loading was axial compression
6 from the gravity loads and bending due to thermal and live loads. Because of the mixed test results from
7 the previous studies, i.e., some indicating good performance while others indicating questionable
8 performance, there was a need for a laboratory testing to better understand their performance in likely
9 Iowa details and how it might be impacted by different constructed processes. The research team
10 constructed a precast element system for testing in the laboratory and investigated the performance of the
11 grouted reinforcing bar couplers with the connection details similar to those utilized on the Keg Creek
12 Bridge.

13 The experimental program consisted of a series of static load testing, a fatigue testing and
14 evaluation of the chloride penetration resistance for investigating the ability of the grouted reinforcing bar
15 couplers to develop flexural capacity between the precast elements as well as the short- and long-term
16 durability of the connection. The main focus of the structural load testing was to assess the performance
17 of the couplers in regards to the formation of crack and the magnitude of the crack width under loading as
18 well as the closure of the crack after the removal of the load. Three loading cases were utilized in the
19 structural load testing – bending, axial load plus bending, and a cyclic test in bending. Seven full-scale
20 specimens were fabricated with varying joint preparations and joint grouts but all specimens included #14
21 epoxy-coated reinforcing bars spliced by epoxy-coated grouted reinforcing bar couplers as was used on
22 the Keg Creek Bridge.

23 The static load testing conducted on six of the specimens showed that the applied axial load had a
24 minimal effect on the formation of cracks and overall performance of the connection. When UHPC was
25 used as a bedding grout, the initiation of the crack was slightly delayed but no considerable improvement
26 was observed in terms of the magnitude of the crack width during loading or the crack closure upon
27 unloading. The results of the seventh specimen, tested in fatigue to 1 million cycles, showed little global
28 displacement and crack width throughout the test, neither of which expanded measurably. Overall, the
29 structural load testing demonstrated that the empirical calculations and the design assumptions utilized
30 during the design of the specimens were valid.

31 For the second aspect of the laboratory testing (i.e., an investigation of the susceptibility of the
32 spliced connection to chloride penetration), three small specimens were cast with the same reinforcing
33 and grout materials used on the Keg Creek Bridge. These specimens were submerged in a 3% chloride
34 solution bath with the joints kept uncracked and monitored for six months. Periodic readings taken during
35 the six months of monitoring and visual inspection at the conclusion of the testing showed that there was
36 no evidence of corrosion or chloride penetration in the connection.

37 Results from this laboratory testing provided confidence to the Iowa DOT engineers in the design
38 of the Keg Creek Bridge replacement project and allowed for the quick, secure connections necessary to
39 reopen the bridge with a minimal traffic closure. Furthermore, the combination of the laboratory testing
40 and the success of the Keg Creek Bridge project led to a series of additional laboratory testing of the
41 grouted rebar couplers utilized in the integral abutment connections for ABC projects (11).
42

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47

48 **AUTHOR CONTRIBUTIONS**

49 The authors confirm contribution to the paper as follows: study conception and design: T. Hosteng, B.
50 Phares; data collection: T. Hosteng; analysis and interpretation of results: T. Hosteng, B. Phares., J.

- 1 Nelson; draft manuscript preparation: Y.S. Lee. All authors reviewed the results and approved the final
- 2 version of the manuscript.

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